

EDUCATIONAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL PERCEPTION IN BLIND SCHOOLCHILDREN

Sevara Fayzieva

Nizami National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan

1st year master's student in the specialty of Music Education and Art

A.Kh.Trigulova

Professor, Nizami National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the pedagogical conditions for developing musical perception in visually impaired schoolchildren as a key component of their general and artistic development. It explores the unique aspects of musical perception in children with visual impairments, which are shaped by the heightened role of auditory, tactile, and emotional experiences, as well as the specific nature of their sensory and cognitive development.

Introduction.

In the modern educational process of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the issues of inclusive education and the creation of conditions for the full development of children with disabilities. One of the urgent tasks of music pedagogy is the formation of musical perception in blind schoolchildren. Music is an important means of aesthetic education, development of the emotional sphere and cognitive activity of students.

Musical perception is understood as a complex psychological and pedagogical process, which includes emotional experience, comprehension and evaluation of a musical work. It is associated with an understanding of the intonational and expressive means of musical language, as well as with a personal experience of the artistic content of the work.

For children with visual impairments, music takes on special meaning. Limited visual impressions enhance the role of the auditory analyzer and also contribute to the development of compensatory mechanisms of perception. In this regard, music education can become an important factor in the development of cognitive activity, imagination and emotional responsiveness of blind schoolchildren.

The purpose of this article is to consider pedagogical conditions that contribute to the effective formation of musical perception in blind schoolchildren.

Theoretical foundations of the formation of musical perception. Musical perception is an active process of interaction between the listener and a piece of music. It includes an emotional response to music, an understanding of its figurative content and awareness of expressive means. In the process of listening to music, students form musical ideas, develop auditory memory, attention and imagination.

Researchers note that the development of musical perception occurs most effectively with the active participation of students in various types of musical activities: listening to music, singing, rhythmic exercises and discussing the artistic content of works.

Pedagogy also emphasizes the need to form a system of auditory reference points in schoolchildren and develop musical-auditory thinking. This contributes to a deeper understanding of the structure of a musical work and the development of the ability to perceive intonation and rhythmic features of music.

In blind children, the perception of the world around them is carried out mainly through auditory and tactile sensations. The absence or partial damage to the visual information channel leads to increased development of auditory attention, memory and the ability to finely distinguish sound characteristics. In this context, music acts not only as a means of aesthetic education, but also performs an important compensatory function, partially making up for the lack of visual perception. Thanks to its expressive and emotional potential, it promotes the active development of imaginative thinking, helping children form internal ideas about the world around them.

Musical activity also plays a significant role in the development of emotional responsiveness, allowing you to more deeply experience and comprehend various states and feelings. In addition, through the perception and interpretation of musical works, students' ideas about the phenomena of reality expand, their life experience is enriched and a more holistic picture of the world is formed.

For blind schoolchildren, verbal descriptions of musical images play an important role. The teacher helps students imagine the nature of the music, its mood and emotional content, using figurative and accessible verbal characteristics.

In addition, the development of auditory memory and inner hearing ability is of great importance, which allows students to better understand the structure of musical works.

Effective formation of musical perception in blind schoolchildren is possible if a number of pedagogical conditions are met.

1. Creating a psychologically comfortable educational environment in the classroom. First of all, in the process of music education for blind schoolchildren, it is necessary to create special pedagogical conditions that provide psychological comfort, emotional security and a sense of confidence for the student, which contributes to his emancipation and free self-expression.

2. Creation of an emotionally rich educational environment. Music classes should evoke an emotional response and interest in music in students. Emotional experience is the basis for the formation of artistic perception and contributes to a deeper understanding of musical content.

3. The use of various types of musical activities: listening to music, vocal activity, rhythmic exercises and elementary music playing. Such diversity contributes to the active involvement of students in the musical process and the development of their auditory perceptions. It is important to add exercises accompanied by physical actions in your work. This helps the student "feel" the music, deeply comprehend its rhythmic and intonation structure, activate sensorimotor sensations and contributes to a more holistic perception of the musical work.

4. Development of auditory attention and memory as a result of auditory analysis of musical material. Students learn to distinguish timbre, rhythm, dynamics and other expressive means of music.

5. Individual approach to learning. Taking into account the peculiarities of perception and the level of musical development of each student, the teacher must use an individual approach, selecting appropriate methods and tasks.

Conclusion. The formation of musical perception in blind schoolchildren is an important task of music pedagogy. Music promotes the development of the emotional sphere, auditory attention and creative imagination of children with visual impairments. The effectiveness of this process depends on the organization of the educational environment, the use of various types of musical activities, the development of auditory abilities and the use of special pedagogical methods. Compliance with these pedagogical conditions makes it possible to improve the quality of music education and contribute to the harmonious development of the personality of blind schoolchildren..

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